

Transactional Leadership Style in Higher Educations: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of the transactional leadership style on staff involvement and student academic learning outcomes at higher education institutions. The transactional leadership approach focuses on structured performance management, clear expectations, and a system of rewards and penalties, promoting organizational efficiency. This paper reviews the current framework and examines how this leadership style influences teacher job satisfaction, professional achievement, and student engagement, ultimately enhancing student academic success. The study aims to explore whether transactional leadership, when applied in educational environments, positively impacts both teacher performance and student learning outcomes. Through a review of the literature and empirical analysis, this research provides insights into the effectiveness of transactional leadership in shaping higher educational outcomes, highlighting both its benefits and limitations.

Keywords: *transactional leadership, academic performance, job satisfaction, higher education.*

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Introduction

The role of transactional leaders in higher education has received increased attention across a number of disciplines in recent years. Transactional leaders have been the focus of research since the 1970s, as they monitor departures from established normative standards and concentrate on the trade relationships between themselves and their followers (Bass 1985; House 1971, 1996).

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Transactional leadership has been studied by many researchers, and effective leadership influences followers' motivation and guides them toward the achievement of (collective) goals (e.g., Bass 1990; Stogdill 1950; House (1971); Bryman (1996)). Since it was reported by Jago (1982) that leadership is expressed or displayed through interpersonal interaction and necessarily implies followership, its complement. Transactional leadership is characterized by leader–follower exchanges, whereby leaders exchange values with followers to advance both leaders' and followers' agendas, according to Ivey and Kline (2010). Recently, there has been new interest in transactional leadership styles such as Ojokuku, Odetayo, and Sajuiyigbe (2012), and a company's leadership style is a key factor in determining its performance, particularly in Nigerian banks. Being a leader means having a vision and being able to put it into action by motivating people to reach new heights and emphasizing the value of good corporate and interpersonal citizenship practices.

The study, the Impact of the Transactional Leadership Style in Higher Institutions: A Systematic Literature Review, aims to explore how transactional leadership impacts staff involvement and student academic learning outcomes in higher institutions. It seeks to examine the effectiveness of this leadership style in promoting structured performance, teacher job satisfaction, professional achievement, and student engagement, ultimately contributing to academic success.

Literature Review

This chapter begins with the outcome variable (transactional leadership, extrinsic reward, incentive framework, result-based) and predictor variable (job satisfaction, professional achievement, student involvement and effort, students' learning outcome). Next, a review of the literature concerning transactional leadership, which involves these teaching behaviors, is presented. Related theories and research studies involve a discussion of each variable. Finally, conclusions are drawn to clarify the study variables. The purpose of this review is to offer a thorough summary and analytical assessment of existing studies on a specific subject.

History of Transactional Leadership Style

Previous studies have reported that in no circumstances that are stable and predictable, the most effective technique is to track activity versus past performance. This is where a skilled transactional leader is likely to be effective. This model of a leader aligns with an equitable leader–member exchange relationship in which the leader provides for followers' needs in return for performance that satisfies fundamental standards (Bass, 1985; Graen & Cashman, 1975). Recent work by Burns (1978) revealed that transformational leadership is inherently moral and grounded in values. This aspect of leadership places a strong emphasis on closely observing followers for any deviations, errors, or blunders so that remedial action can be made as quickly as possible. Although the previously outlined aspects of transformational and transactional leadership have strong empirical support (e.g., Avolio, 1999; Bass, 1998; Bass & Avolio, 2000 ; Huot, et al., 2024; Bou, et al., 2024; Chhor, et al., 2024; Meas, et al., 2024; Yea, et al., 2024; Meas, et al., 2024) by outlining expectations for followers and rewarding the achievement of goals, transactional leaders exemplify contingent rewards. Hackman (2009) noted that management-by-exception upholds the status quo, which steps when subordinates do not perform up to par, and starts corrective action as needed to increase output. Transactional leaders define what constitutes ineffective performance, the criteria for compliance, and the consequences for noncompliance when they implement active management-by-exception (Grove, 2011; Lan, et al, 2024 a; Lan, et al., 2024b; Chork, et al., 2024; Hoernng, et al., 2024). The results of an earlier study by Hargis et al. (2010) revealed a strong and consistent association between transactional leaders and contingent punishments or between transactional leaders and rewards and that transactional leaders are more focused on procedures than innovative concepts are. These leaders emphasize the concept of contingent punishments or

rewards. Contingent rewards, such as praise, are given when objectives are completed on schedule, ahead of schedule, or to maintain subordinates' high level of productivity at various points during the completion process. When performance quality or quantity is below production standards or goals and tasks are not completed at all, contingent punishments (like suspensions) are applied. The focus of management-by-exception is on leadership as a bad habit.

Transactional Leadership Key Elements

It has been conclusively shown that three main focuses of transactional leadership exist: performance, supervision, and organization. To guarantee effective operations, it places a strong emphasis on structure, order, and set regulations. These are the main components (Aorin, 2006).

Clear Expectations: Transactional leaders establish clear goals and performance standards for employees. Transactional leaders are known for their structured approach to management. They believe in creating a clear roadmap for employees to follow.

Incentives Framework: Rewards and punishments are used to motivate employees and ensure compliance with expectations. The study's findings demonstrated a favorable correlation between organizational commitment and transformational and transactional leadership. The findings also showed that transactional leadership styles had a greater effect on Nigerian banking employees' commitment than did transformational leadership styles. According to the report, supervisors should give their staff members positive reinforcement when they perform up to par (Fasola. Et al, 2013). **Focus on Results:** This leadership style prioritizes achieving specific outcomes and objectives. On the other hand, until the issue is fixed, those who possess this leadership style can also penalize subpar performance or unfavorable results. Emphasizing specific job performance is one method by which transactional leadership addresses needs at a lower level (Hargis et al., 2001). Transactional leaders manage each part separately, which helps them execute specialized duties effectively.

Figure 1. Key Elements of Transactional Leadership

Source: Aorin, 2006

Transactional Leadership Style in the Educational Setting in Higher Education

Research on leadership in educational and instructional contexts has been conducted for a long time, and effective leadership has an imperative role in improving the performance and growth of organizations. Most studies focus on a few specific principal-teacher responsibilities, such as curriculum development, teacher evaluation, and goal setting (Day et al., 2016). However, several performance efforts were unsuccessful as a result of factors such as the satisfactory leadership style of leaders. The study examined how academic leaders' performance was impacted by the relationship between transactional (contingent rewards) and transformational leadership styles. Academic administrators would find value in the conclusions of this study. The influence of effective leadership skills on the professional achievement of teachers and the academic success of students has been acknowledged in several studies. Kim et al. (2000), Lee et al. (2009), Ma et al. (2017), and Wubbels and Brekelmans (2005) reported that the classroom environment significantly contributes to student motivation, active engagement, and higher academic performance. This leadership approach is socialization-based interactive leadership. She projected that male executives would adopt a more transactional style of leadership, whereas female leaders would demonstrate a transformative style. As the first component, contingent rewards indicate how transactional leaders award followers in return for the achievement of goals predetermined and announced by the leader. As a result, the teachers who exhibited transactional (Erdal,2020) leadership qualities seemed to be more successful educators, as seen by the fact that their pupils were more engaged in their lessons and gave their all throughout the course.

Previous Study

The findings of the study conducted by Erdal and Tacca (2020) would be useful for academic leaders. This approach is aimed mainly at increasing the effectiveness of higher learning institutions; therefore, they adopt a leadership style that refines the abilities of academic leaders and assists them in attaining profit performance. The aim of this study is to investigate the transformational and transactional leadership styles of school principals and to evaluate them in terms of educational administration. A descriptive survey model was used in the research. The research data were obtained from a total of 1,117 teachers working in public and private schools subjected to the Ministry of National Education in the Avclar district of Istanbul Province in 2014. In this study, data were obtained from the "personal information form" developed by the researcher and from the "leadership styles scale". Data that were obtained from the respondents were entered via the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 17.0, and research data were resolved with "average", "standard deviation", "t test" and "one-way analysis of variance". According to the research results, teachers had a high level of positive opinions with respect to the transformational and transactional leadership characteristics of school principals. Teachers' perceptions of the transformational and transactional leadership characteristics of school principals do not vary significantly according to gender, state of education or professional seniority (Aciv, 2015).

By examining the connections between transformational and transactional leadership and several ethical paradigms that have been proposed as pertinent to resolving moral conundrums in education, the current study bridges this gap. The participants completed the Ethical Perspectives Instrument (EPI) to gauge their moral reasoning in addition to self-reporting their leadership practices. While transactional leadership anticipated applying utilitarian ethics, transformational leadership anticipated turning to the ethics of critique and profession. The results of the study are discussed below (Berkoiwick, 2021).

To ascertain the relationships between instructors' leadership styles and the outcomes of leader effectiveness (the instructor in the classroom context), students' extra effort, and student satisfaction, this study examined the classroom leadership styles of English language teachers

within the full-range leadership (FRL) framework. A Turkish public university recruited 300 students from the English Language Teaching and English Language and Literature Departments to participate in the Classroom Leadership Instrument, a modified version of the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire. Inferential statistical tests were used to assess the research data, and the findings revealed a substantial correlation between all three leadership styles and transformational leadership as well as the active characteristics of transactional leadership results. As a result, teachers who possessed these qualities of leadership emerged. to become more proficient educators whose pupils were happier (Erdel & Tackie, 2020).

Conceptual Framework

Transactional leadership is a type of leadership style in which reward ultimately arouses employees’ motivation to accomplish their goals. There are three key elements of leadership style: clear expectations, the incentive framework and a focus on results. Employing a leadership style in the education setting contributes profound benefits to employees and ensures the general operation of the institution. Employees are satisfied with their job performance when this type of leadership is implicated. The transactional leadership style contributes profound benefits to teachers and students, such as the professional achievement of teachers and the academic success of students. More importantly, it can stimulate students’ motivation, engagement, and academic performance. The moral aspect was found when the leadership style was carried out, which was good for the other style.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework of Transactional Leadership

Materials and Methods

The current literature on the implementation and effects of transformational leadership approaches in higher education institutions is compiled in this study via a systematic literature review

methodology. According to Arksey & O'Malley (2005) and Tricco et al. (2016), a scoping review is a suitable method since it permits a thorough examination of the existing research on the subject without the necessity for a specifically specified research question or the stringent quality appraisal standards of a systematic review.

Research Strategy

The following electronic databases were searched thoroughly and methodically as part of the search strategy: Google Scholar, Eric. Only keyword combinations such as "transactional leadership," "academic performance," "job satisfaction," and "higher education" are included in the search phrases. The scope of the search will be restricted to peer-reviewed journal papers written in English and published between 2014 and 2024. This period of time was chosen to represent the recent surge in interest in and study transactional leadership in higher education. To find any more pertinent publications, the reference lists of the included studies were manually scanned in addition to the database searches. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) standards (Moher et al., 2009) will be followed in the study selection process.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The selection processes are employed according to the following criteria. First, open access publications can be found in international journals and famous textbooks about leadership. Second, the articles and the leadership textbooks published between 2014 and 2024 potentially focused on the key concepts and patterns in the literature related to the implications and impacts of the transactional leadership style in higher education. The pertinent bibliography, key findings, core elements of transactional leadership, outcomes and implications are included in the studies.

Figure 3. PRISMA Flow Diagram

The findings were examined to ensure that they met the research objectives. Initial data screening was conducted via Publish or Perish software. The selection process for research papers followed the four stages described in the PRISMA flow diagram: identification, eligibility, screening, and inclusion. The first stage of article screening involved a database search that yielded 75 articles sourced from Google Scholar (30), ERIC (30), and books (15).

Data Analysis

The thematic analysis employed the key ideas that were extracted from the data and transformed into a long list of themes. The results were reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) guidelines (Tricco et al., 2018). This ensures a clear and concise description of the study's methodology, conclusions, and implications. Visualizations such as tables and figures improve the narrative synthesis and make the findings easier to understand and retrieve. The scoping assessment provides a comprehensive overview of the state of the art in the subject of transformative leadership in higher education, highlighting significant gaps and possible directions for further research. The results have important implications for higher education leaders, researchers and policy makers in being aware of the significance of transactional leadership and effectively and efficiently implementing it in educational settings

Sample

The study explored the significance of the existing published articles in journals that could be used as meta-synthesis data. This study examines articles on the trend of transactional leadership in higher education.

Results

Transactional leadership can motivate employees through extrinsic rewards: when their basic need is fulfilled to a certain extent, they are motivated and satisfied with their job, which results in increased productivity. As Maxwell (2020) mentioned in his book, good leaders inspire others only to the extent that they inspire themselves. Students are motivated and willing to participate in class activities when extrinsic rewards are offered. Learning can occur when there is a series of external reinforcements (i.e., rewards) or punishments for elicited behaviors (B. F Skinner, 1950). Happiness, collaboration, and well-being are all cultivated via connection; the more giving we are, the more our hearts open, and the more joy we feel (Bunting, 2016).

Transactional leadership indirectly influences the generation of organization- and student-focused ideas through employee commitment: bringing together to work is the transactional leadership's jog by giving a reward in return. When the incentive has been offered, they possess a strong commitment, and they scarify themselves for the benefits of the organization. Michael Bunting (2017) mentioned that mindfulness provides us with the awareness to acknowledge our accountability and equips us with the tools to adopt a new way of thinking, acting, and perceiving the world. Indeed, from a pedagogical perspective, contingent reward behaviors correspond to *positive feedback*, which refers to teacher actions of affirmative response to correct answers from students, and it is considered important since it provides the learner with *affective support* and further increases motivation for learning (Ellis, 2009).

School principals exhibit strong transactional leadership qualities with no significant differences across demographics. School principals' leadership should focus on addressing challenges effectively while unifying all aspects of the institution, regardless of sex, length of service, workplace, and age. As Jim Kouzes and Barry Posner noted in their book, *"A leader's dynamism doesn't come from special powers. It comes from a strong belief in a purpose and a willingness to express that*

conviction". A good leader has special talent to help others build the gap between their work and purpose, to motivate others to work, to help them see the purpose and vision and to communicate the purpose effectively by doing (Shahar & Ridgway, 2017).

The transactional leadership classroom is correlated with greater student satisfaction and effort: Students learn through cooperative interaction and experience, and it is an engagement in worthwhile activity rather than the passive absorption of fact (Lenunbug, 2004). The teacher is not the person who provides all the information to students but the one who facilitates the learner's learning process. Tee (2005) mentioned that synergistic results arise when people are brought together to test ideas, discuss what they are learning, assist others in new ways, and listen to one other's stories. According to Lord et al. (1999), transactional leaders stipulate that rewards are dependent on accomplishments, which can highlight individual task performance and help followers differentiate themselves from one another in terms of their accomplishments.

Transformational leadership aligns with the ethics of critique, whereas transactional leadership corresponds to utilitarian ethics. Value is the most important thing on earth. Courage and confidence somehow stem from value or ethics. Being a good leader is only one aspect of living with integrity and in accordance with our principles. It is also about being content with our life and ourselves, and it helps us see things clearly when those around us are motivated by fear, worry, or other undesirable traits (Wisely, 2017). Transactional leaders are ethical leaders that emphasize honesty, responsibility, mutual respect and teamwork. Mashell required a company that was committed to helping people, behaving with integrity, respecting each person, encouraging teamwork, and cultivating a feeling of accountability for the airline's performance and direction (Lee & Cosgrove, 2018). According to Cashman's book, trust and courage are the cornerstones of progressive and long-lasting leadership performance; trust keeps us united when we walk into the unknown, whereas courage gives us the strength to shape the future.

Teachers with transactional leadership styles positively influence school outcomes. Transactional leadership has two important traits that strongly affect organizational outcomes. The transactional leader focuses on maintaining current performance through strict oversight and control (Cashman, 2017). Indeed, from a pedagogical perspective, contingent reward behaviors correspond to *positive feedback*, which refers to teacher actions of affirmative response to correct answers from students, and it is considered important since it provides the learner with *affective support* and further increases motivation for learning (Ellis, 2009). Many researchers have suggested that corrective feedback is important in the development of writing skills (Bitchener & Ferris, 2012; Ellis, 2009; Ferris & Roberts, 2001).

Discussion

While effective in certain contexts, transactional leadership can have both positive and negative impacts on staff involvement and student academic outcomes in high school. While it can provide clear expectations, structure, and motivation through rewards and punishments, it may also lead to decreased morale, reduced creativity, and limited engagement among staff. To create a more effective and supportive school environment, it is essential to balance transactional leadership with other approaches, such as transformational leadership, which focuses on inspiring and empowering individuals. This study concludes that **transactional leadership** can be highly effective in achieving specific academic and organizational goals in high school settings, particularly those focused on clear performance outcomes and structure.

Conclusion

By providing well-defined expectations and incentive frameworks, transactional leaders can improve both teacher performance and student academic achievement. Recent evidence suggests that people who are motivated by the moral aspect of doing good for others are found in the teaching profession and in all types of schools, both public and private. Therefore, transactional leadership is more likely to occur than in many other professions since intrinsic rewards—doing something good for the students—are as high as enhancing teachers' work conditions (extrinsic rewards) for the majority of teachers (Macmill, 2018). As a result, the teachers who exhibited these leadership qualities seemed to be more successful educators, as their pupils were more engaged in their lessons and gave their all throughout the course. It was defined by Rosener (1990). However, the transactional approach also has limitations, especially in environments where creativity, innovation, and long-term motivation are crucial.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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Appendix

Table 1. The Study of Highlights the synthesis of the Literature on the Application and Impact of Transactional Leadership in the Context of Higher Educations

N ^o	Year	Author(s)	Topic article/Title	Types of tests/Publisher	Key finding/Key ideas	Implication
1	2021	Neil MacNeill	Transformational and Transactional Leadership: a False Dichotomy of Leadership in Schools	The interview for the principal's position	As a result, it would seem that extrinsic, pecuniary rewards may be used to define transactional leadership. Every motivational move to action transactional leadership is the key factor for every motivational move to action	Extrinsic, pecuniary benefits might constitute transactional leadership; yet, each person has opinions about the individual advantages of each modification, and participants continuously assess this dynamic equation throughout time.
2	2014	Dirk Deichmann and Daan Stam	Leveraging Transformational and Transactional Leadership to Cultivate the Generation of Organization -focused Ideas	Employed two layers of data analysis using hierarchical linear modeling: department leader (level 2) and employee (level 1).	The results confirm that there is a significant indirect effect of transactional leadership on the generation of organization-focused ideas via employee commitment to the ideation program.	This leadership style might therefore, at least in some contexts, be more motivating to followers
3	2016	Kevin B.Lowe, K. Galen Kroeck, and Nagaraj Sivassubramaniam	Effectiveness Correlation of Transformational and Transactional Leadership:	Using the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ), a meta-analysis of the literature on transformational leadership was carried out.	The scale of transactions, contingent reward has also been linked to effectiveness. When large, the transactional scale Management-by-Exception is frequently negative and has little relationship to effectiveness.	Unexpected results on the prevalence of transformative leader behavior and its connections to effectiveness are examined for the type of company and leader level.
4.	2015	Ahmet Avci	Investigation of Transformational and Transactional leadership Styles of School Principals and Evaluation of Them in Terms of Educational Administration	Data were collected using a "personal information form" created by the researcher, along with the "leadership styles scale." The responses were entered into the Statistical Package Analysis of the research data involved calculating the "mean,"	Teachers expressed strong positive views on the transactional leadership qualities of school principals. Their perceptions of these leadership characteristics showed no significant differences based on gender, educational background, or years of professional experience.	Along with leading change within the school, school principals' leadership qualities should enable them to address problems swiftly and effectively. Their leadership should serve as a cohesive force, bringing together all tangible and

				"standard deviation," and applying both the "t test" and "one-way analysis of variance" (ANOVA).		intangible aspects of the school, creating a unified and consistent whole.
5	2020	Didem Erdel, Mehmet Takkec	Instructor Leadership in EFL Classrooms and the Outcomes: The effects of Transformational and Transactional Leadership Styles	The Classroom Leadership Instrument, an adapted version of the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire, was given to 300 students. Inferential statistical tests were used to analyze the research data.	Instructors with transactional leadership qualities seemed to be more effective teachers, as their students reported higher levels of satisfaction with their teaching and demonstrated greater effort in their courses.	To enhance comprehensiveness, future research could explore the same scope in varied contexts with different participant groups.
6	2020	Izhak Berkovich, Ori Eyal	Transformational Leadership, Transactional Leadership and Moral Reasoning.	Participants self-reported on their leadership behaviors, and the Ethical Perspectives Instrument (EPI) was administered to assess their moral reasoning.	Transformational leadership predicted resorting to the ethics of critique and profession, whereas transactional leadership predicted use of the ethics of utilitarianism.	the two ethical patterns represent ethical leadership, which assumes responsibility and expresses its personal moral commitment in dialog with structural and systemic constraints.
7	2017	Irungu Njoroge, John Wekesa, Bulitia Godrick Mathews	Transactional leadership Style and Organization Commitment: The Moderating Effect of Employee Participation	The population comprised of 3114 lecturers while 343 respondents made up the sample. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics and multiple regression.	The results indicated that transactional leadership style had a significant effect on organizational commitment.	
8	2018	Yeliz Erath Sirin, Ozge Aydm, Fatma Pervin Bilir	Transformational - Transactional Leadership and Organizational Cynicism Perception: Physical Education and Sport	. Descriptive statistics were applied to analyze the collected data. Kurtosis and skewness values were examined to assess the normality of variable distributions. For data analysis, paired comparisons were conducted using a t test	Physical education teachers had moderate degrees of organizational cynicism and higher opinions of transformational leadership than they did of transactional leadership.	To improve teacher performance and educational quality, it is advised that similar studies be carried out on teachers from various branches using qualitative data collection techniques.
10	2020	Didem Erdel, Mehmet Takkac	Teacher Leadership Inside the Classroom: Implications for Effective Language Teaching	The study used a mixed methods approach, including in-person interviews with instructors and students, a questionnaire survey that	The findings showed that while teachers with higher passive transactional and laissez-faire leadership scores were correspondingly less effective in	Effective leadership in the classroom is attributed to transformational and active transactional leadership traits, and incorporating

				contained the Classroom Leadership Instrument. In addition to the four professors instructing the course, 18 of the 305 students who completed the survey were questioned further. Descriptive tests were used to analyze quantitative data, while content analysis was used to examine observations and interviews.	both teaching activities and their relationships with the students, those with higher tendencies for transformational and active components of transactional styles were rather more organized, enthusiastic, and committed, and their students attributed these traits to them as more positive and effective.	these traits into instructional strategies and teacher-student interactions may provide fruitful results.
11	2021	Hasan Yucel Ertem	Relationship of School Leadership with School Outcome: A meta-analysis Study	A meta-analysis of 21 studies conducted within the Turkish context was carried out to fulfill the study's objectives.	Thelaissez-faire, transactional, instructional, and transformational leadership styles were found to have a significant and positive relationship with school outcomes overall.	it is recommended that future studies develop a leadership theory specific to the educational settings in Turkey.
12	2021	Esia-Donkoh, Kweku, and Quansah, David Kwame	Education Quarterly Reivews	Used a quantitative approach with a cross-sectional survey design. A census sampling technique was applied to include 38 principals in the study. Data were collected using an adapted version of the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) by Bass and Avolio (2004).	The inferential analyses showed no statistically significant differences in principals' leadership styles based on the setting, zone, or location of the colleges.	GTEC should prioritize competence when selecting and appointing principals, rather than considering the setting, zone, or location of public Colleges of Education, since it did not significantly influence the leadership styles principals adopted.
13	2021	Norhaily Abdul Halim, Aminuddin Hassan, Ramli Basri, Aminuddin Yussof, Seyedali Ahrari	Job Satifaction as a Mediator between Leadership styles and Organizational Commitment of Teachers in Malaysia	The study, conducted with 381 school teachers in Malaysia, utilized multiple-model analysis, which demonstrated partial mediation in the negative relationship between passive-avoidant leadership style and teachers' organizational commitment.	Job satisfaction fully mediated the relationship between transactional leadership and organizational commitment among teachers. Teachers who were highly satisfied with their jobs attributed their commitment to their school to transactional leadership.	leadership development and training of future school administrators during their tertiary education are important in order to enhance teachers' job satisfaction and commitment.

14	2021	Tazeen Ather and Riffat-un-NIisa Awan	Effect of Knowledge Management Practices and Leadership Styles of Heads of Department on University Teachers' Performance	The study employed a quantitative descriptive research design with a conveniently selected sample of 260 faculty members. Data were gathered using three five-point Likert scale instruments.	The findings indicated that both transformational and transactional leaders engaged in knowledge sharing and have a significant influence of leadership styles on university teacher performance, as well as a notable impact of knowledge management practices on teacher performance.	This study offers insights into which leadership style is most effective in enhancing university teachers' performance through knowledge practices.
15	2023	Kaitlin M. Jackson	Perceptions of Leadership Styles in International Special and General Education School in the United Arab Emirates.	Using primarily quantitative methods complemented by qualitative analysis, this study examined how teacher demographic variables impact perceptions of leadership styles.	Perceptions of transformational and transactional leadership across different school types based on teachers' education levels and differences in perceptions of passive-avoidant leadership by school type related to teachers' total years of experience with the school leader.	These include suggestions for professional development, school policy development, and the consideration of culture as an expanded demographic variable of interest.
16	2022	Emmett Lombard	Do You Want This Double OR Single Spaced? Transactional Versus Transformational Questions	The study observed 162 undergraduate students across nine sections of four different courses in three formats (in-person, online, and hybrid) over a two-year period.	Transactional questions do not promote learning, as they are primarily focused on completing tasks, similar to how a transactional leader prioritizes immediate, specific details over a broader, long-term vision.	The paper concludes with recommendations for the higher education sector that could help foster a more transformational mindset among students.
17	2023	Peng Liu, Lili Liu, Yalong Bo, Hui Yang	Exploring the relationships between perceived transformational leadership and transactional leadership and teacher's intellectual style	This study examined 967 middle school teachers from four cities in a single province in China, using convenience sampling. In China, principals are mandated to regularly engage in professional development programs. A questionnaire survey was administered to gather data from schools where a group of principals, who participated in these professional development	There is a positive correlation between teachers' perception of transactional leadership and their intellectual style II. Transactional leadership centers on the exchange of rewards between leaders and followers, offering benefits in return for compliance. This management method requires teachers only to work hard under strict rules, which reduces the teachers' creativity and their courage to conduct creative work	School administrators should move beyond strict organizational control and restrictions on teachers' autonomy. This approach will help facilitate effective change within the school organization.

				programs, had worked between April and July 2020.		
18	2023	Zhao Cheng, Chang Zhu	Leadership Styles of Mid-level Educational Leaders Perceived by Academic Members: An Exploratory Study among Chinese Universities.	Qualitative research was carried out to explore the perceptions of 13 academic staff members from nine universities in China.	The study found that the authoritarian leadership style was the most commonly reported among mid-level educational leaders, followed by transformational and transactional leadership styles.	The study's implications could guide the development of future leadership training programs in Chinese higher education institutions.
19	2024	Virgana Virganna, Merry Lapasau	Elevating Teachers' Performance through Locus of Control, Leadership Style, Environmental Factors, and Work Motivation.	A sample of 720 high school teachers was used to examine the perceptions of locus of control, leadership style, environmental factors, and work motivation on performance. The data were then analyzed using Smart-Partial Least Squares software.	The results revealed a direct impact of locus of control, leadership style, and environmental factors on work motivation. These findings underscore the importance of having qualified teachers, a need must address to improve education nationwide.	Enhancing environmental factors will increase teachers' motivation and productivity in teaching and learning activities, ultimately improving their work performance.
20	2024	Jose Z.Tria	Transactional Distance in a Flexible Learning Environment: Scale Development and Validation in the Philippine Context.	Cronbach's alpha was applied to test the internal consistency of the items. The model revealed a three-factor structure based on Moore's Transactional Distance theory, namely, structure, learner autonomy, and dialog.	The transactional distance scale in a flexible learning environment could help support the successful implementation of flexible learning in higher education institutions, ensuring it is carried out effectively and efficiently.	Policymakers with a tool to assess the implementation of flexible learning, thereby enhancing teaching and learning practices in higher education institutions.
21	2017	Thoma H.Lee, MD and Toby Cosgrove, MD	On Leadership for Healthcare	Havard Business Review Press Boston, Massacuhsetts	Discipline people, discipline though and disciplined action.	When disciplined thinking is in place, bureaucracy becomes unnecessary; when disciplined action is practiced, excessive controls are not needed. By blending a culture of discipline with an entrepreneurial mindset, you achieve the powerful formula for exceptional performance.
22	2017	Tal Ben-Sharhar and Angus Rideway	The Joy of Leadership	Wiley India Pvt.Ltd, Ansari Road, Daryaganj, New Delhi	Passion Strength and Performance strength.	Many individuals possess strengths that remain hidden and untapped, and

						uncovering them is the first step toward personal growth. Passion strengths are the ones that ignite a spark within you, motivating you to leverage your talents. Performance strengths, on the other hand, are the skills you already excel at or have the greatest potential to master.
23	2004	Fred C.Lunenburg and Allan C.Ornstein.	Educational Administration	Edith Beard Brady	Humanistic school	Students learn through cooperative interaction and experience and it is an engagement in worthwhile activity rather than the passive absorption of fact
24	2017	Michael Bunting	The Mindful Leader: 7 practices for Transforming, your organization and your life	Wiley India Pvt.Ltd, Ansari Road, Daryaganj, New Delhi	Accountability is a core mindfulness (page 29)	Mindfulness provides us with the awareness to acknowledge our accountability and equips us with the tools to adopt a new way of thinking, acting, and perceiving the world, ultimately reducing our own suffering and that of others.
25	2017	Kevin Cashman	Leadership From The Inside Out	Barreth-Koehler Publisher, Inc.	Serve authentically (page 122)	A leader is evaluated not merely by their ability to lead but by their capacity to serve. All values and contributions stem from acts of service. Leadership is an ongoing journey of service, encompassing support for the organization, team members, customers, community, and family. Relationships thrive when

						they are built on the foundation of mutual benefit and service.
26	2020	John C.Maxwell	The Leader's Greatest Return	Published in association with Yates & Yates, www.yates2.com	Attitude of the Potential Leaders: "Are they Willing?"	Effective leaders desire more success and growth for the people they lead than they seek to gain from them. I have long emphasized to aspiring leaders that people won't care about the extent of your knowledge until they see the depth of your care for them.

